

Symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments

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symbloTe Virtual IoT Environment Implementation

The symbloTe Consortium

Intracom SA Telecom Solutions, ICOM, Greece
Sveučiliste u Zagrebu Fakultet elektrotehnike i računarstva, UNIZG-FER, Croatia
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH, AIT, Austria
Nextworks Srl, NXW, Italy
Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni, CNIT, Italy
ATOS Spain SA, ATOS, Spain
University of Vienna, Faculty of Computer Science, UNIVIE, Austria
Unidata S.p.A., UNIDATA, Italy
Sensing & Control System S.L., S&C, Spain
Fraunhofer IOSB, IOSB, Germany
Ubiwhere, Lda, UW, Portugal
VIPnet, d.o.o, VIP, Croatia
Instytut Chemii Bioorganicznej Polskiej Akademii Nauk, PSNC, Poland
NA.VI.GO. SCARL, NAVIGO, Italy

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For more information on this document or the symbloTe project, please contact:
Sergios Soursos, INTRACOM TELECOM, souse@intracom-telecom.com

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Editor(s): Tomasz Rajtar

E-mail: tomasz.rajtar@man.poznan.pl

Author(s): Tomasz Rajtar, Szymon Mueller, Marcin Plociennik, Artur Jaworski, Michal Urbaniak, Mateusz Lukaszenko, Matteo Pardi, Elena Garrido Ostermann, Vasileios Glykantzis,

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1 Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to document the first release of the symbloTe software components. The symbloTe project has a challenging task of implementing IoT platforms cooperation environment, enabling the platforms to interoperate, collaborate and share resources. Our goal is also to give the client applications a uniform interface to access various types of the IoT platforms.

We are using previous symbloTe deliverables, especially Deliverable 1.2 [1], as input points to our work. Already existing symbloTe analyses in case of the requirements, use-cases, system architecture and semantic data models have made foundation for software development. The symbloTe architecture (see Deliverable 1.2 [1]) is defining various levels of integration with symbloTe services for platform providers. In this context, the functionality of the first software release is focusing on essential features allowing to achieve Level 1 of symbloTe compliance (L1 Compliance). the goal was to implement and integrate the essential features, e.g., registration and update of IoT platforms and resources, handling simple search requests for resources, access to the virtualized resources returned from the search.

The design of current release elements contains components grouped in domains, describes their roles, interactions and communication interfaces – all these aspects are covered in details in the current document.

The main outcome of this deliverable is the source code and its documentation, published as an open source project in the GitHub service. This document is showing how this software is organized, how it is currently operating and which functionalities are provided to the IoT platforms. The symbloTe software is still under development and its functionalities will grow in next releases planned for the first half of 2017.

The list of components implemented for Release 1 is as follows:

- Core Services layer:
 - *Core Interface* - defines a unique way of interaction for end users and third-party client applications
 - *Administration* - allows to register new symbloTe users and platforms
 - *Registry* - handles registration of symbloTe resources in core layer
 - *Search* - allows client applications to search for resources registered in *symbloTe*
 - *Core Resource Access Monitor* – acts as a proxy which redirects client applications to the actual resources offered by symbloTe-enabled platforms
 - *Cloud-Core Interface* – a gateway from core services to supported symbloTe-enabled IoT platforms
- Cloud Domain (IoT platform related part of the system):
 - *Interworking Interface* - gateway for communication of symbloTe platform-related components with the external world
 - *Registration Handler* - allows an IoT platform to register and update its resources with symbloTe Core Services
 - *Resource Access Proxy* - enables symbloTe-compliant access to resources within an IoT Platform

2 Introduction

2.1 Document scope

This report is a description of the current (Release 1) status of implementation of the symbloTe software components belonging to Level 1 of symbloTe compliance mode (short version: L1). Currently 10 components have been implemented and integrated, 1 additional component have been conceptually designed.

This document also describes the basis of the design decisions, the ideas that are supporting symbloTe software design and it covers the topic of current progress of the implementation. The already existing outcome from symbloTe's workpackages (WP1 works on requirements and architecture, WP2 Task 2.1 works on semantics) gave us a foundation for implementation of the symbloTe Release 1 components, so we are very shortly summarizing their outcomes (only from the current implementation point of view). Finally, there is a description of what have been done until the date of this document release, regarding the symbloTe L1 software development.

2.2 Document structure

The main part of the document starts in chapter 3, which contains a short summary of symbloTe reports that were leading us into current software implementation. Our goal was to show, in a very short manner, the progress from requirements, through architecture, to the design decisions in the implementation phase.

Chapter 4 contains description of the existing components that are currently under development, the current state of component's features, and a list of usage scenarios are supported by the first symbloTe Release.

The main outcome of Task 2.2 is the first symbloTe software release (Release 1), published on the project's GitHub repository (<https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/>). The repository contains the source code of implemented components, their Javadoc documentation, configurations, additional services (like demo web application). In this context Chapter 5 is a short, tabular overview of the existing L1 components and refers to the GitHub resources (links included in tables).

3 Preliminaries

3.1 Requirements and use-case analysis

The main objective of the symbloTe project relevant to the first software release is to create a mediation framework to enable discovery and sharing of connected devices across existing and future IoT platforms. This framework will enable platform federations and rapid development of cross-platform IoT applications.

To achieve the project goals the first steps were taken in workpackage WP1, initial analysis of requirements and use cases were performed. It is not the scope of this document to repeat conclusions from already existing reports, but of course implementation is an action following these works. For further details in terms of use cases and requirements please refer to D1.1 [2] and D1.2 [1] respectively. After the definition of system requirements, the symbloTe consortium has defined initial architecture of the system in D1.2 [1], which is a direct foundation for software implementation (and this report).

3.2 symbloTe architecture

As it was already stated in detail in the symbloTe's report on system architecture [1], the symbloTe approach is built around a layered IoT stack connecting various devices (sensors, actuators and IoT gateways) within Smart Spaces with the Cloud. Smart Spaces share the available local resources (connectivity, computing and storage), while platform services running in the Cloud enable IoT Platform Federations and open up the Interworking Interface to third parties. The architecture comprises four layered domains, as depicted in Figure 1 (for detailed meaning of layers please refer to report [1]): 1) the Application domain, 2) the Cloud domain, 3) the Smart Space domain and 4) the Device domain.

Figure 1 The symbloTe high-level architecture

SymbloTe is aiming to create flexible interoperability mechanisms which can be achieved by introducing an incremental deployment of symbloTe functionality across the listed architectural domains (APP, CLD, SSP and SD). We suppose that this approach will enable platform providers to choose an appropriate level of integration of symbloTe-specific services within their platforms, which will in effect influence the level of platform collaboration and cooperation with other platforms within a symbloTe-enabled ecosystem.

Figure 2 symbloTe Compliance Levels

There are four different Compliance Levels for IoT platforms defined, as depicted in Figure 2. They reflect different interoperability modes, which an IoT platform can support. Different interoperability modes affect the functionality that needs to be supported by platforms, and require specific symbloTe components to be integrated within different domains.

Current release implementation is aiming to provide components that are supporting Level 1 compliance mode. L1 relates to services placed in two domains, APP and CLD, as depicted in Figure 3. IoT platforms which want to become part of the symbloTe ecosystem need to integrate the symbloTe Interworking Interface with its existing components running in the Cloud Domain. This will enable semantic interoperability and open access to IoT services that a platform chooses to register and make discoverable via the symbloTe Core Services. Access to these devices will stay under the control of a platform provider, while being enabled through the Interworking Interface. In addition to open access, symbloTe also supports authenticated and authorized access to IoT services.

Figure 3 Level 1 Compliance

3.3 System design for implementation phase

3.3.1 Architecture ideas

The symbloTe Level 1 architecture was outlined in [1] in the form presented in Figure 4. It is clearly visible, that this set of functional system components repeats the layered idea of the L1 system outline shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 4 Component diagram for Level 1 Compliance

The essential set of components and interfaces implemented in Release 1 is marked red in Figure 4. In the current release we aimed to implement a sub-set of system features. They are related to the components marked by the red outlines in the Figure 4. Components selected for the first implementation cycle create the L1 architecture for Release 1 and this is shown in a simpler form in Figure 5.

Detailed descriptions of each component’s features implemented in the current release are described in the following chapters, therefore, in this chapter, we will focus on component design, communication flow and supporting the data models.

3.3.2 Semantic interoperability and data models

The overall objective of symbloTe is to create an interoperability framework for IoT platforms and to enable platform federation. In this scope, achieving semantic interoperability is a key challenge. From the beginning, symbloTe plans to use semantic technologies to bridge the gap between existing and future IoT platforms with a goal to enable interoperability on the semantic level. For detailed description of symbloTe's semantic interoperability level issues, please refer to the Deliverable D2.1 “*Semantics for IoT and Cloud resources*” [3].

Figure 5 Release 1 system design

Figure 6 symbloTe Meta Information Model (MIM), current version 0.2

The main output of work performed by symbloTe's semantics interoperability team are recommendations and information models, both general and tailored to the needs of symbloTe consortium's IoT platforms. In the current implementation, we are using the following symbloTe information models: Meta Information Model (MIM, see Figure 6) and Core Information Model (CIM, see Figure 7).

MIM provides the concepts needed to describe platforms metadata that are registered in symbloTe.

CIM comprises all the metadata about resources exposed by platforms connected to symbloTe that symbloTe can understand, which are essential for symbloTe Core Services.

Our current approach is to utilize semantic web technology stack inside the Core Services. Information models are a basis for platform and resources registration, modification and search functionality.

Strict Resource Description Framework (RDF) is currently used internally by Search component. In Release 1 a simplified API (REST with JSON payloads) to semantic data models is provided. In the next releases the system will also include RDF related endpoints, in application-side and platform-side interfaces, to let the end users use the full potential of SPARQL queries and semantic data models.

3.3.3 Implementation design

One of the first conclusions of the requirements analysis and creation of the first architecture outlines, was that the potential load of requests to the central, core services can be huge. Potentially thousands of end-user client applications are expected to simultaneously access or search for interesting resources in hundreds (from thousands) of sensors/actuators provided by hundreds of IoT platform instances. Although the numbers seem high, but this is quite a probable scenario in a fully-fledged, interworking IoT environment.

This lead us to the following implications:

- We are building a large-scale distributed system.
- System architecture has to naturally support horizontal scaling.
- We have to offer a simple REST interface of the Core Services for end-clients, both end-user applications and IoT platforms. It is also possible during implementation, that some of these REST end points will have to be designed in an asynchronous way (e.g. by the call-back mechanisms implementation)
- To be able to handle the load of requests, the internal communication between components should be non-blocking (asynchronous).
- Due to scalability and performance issues, the internal system components, especially in case of the Core Services, have to be designed as autonomous, loosely coupled working services with well-established interfaces.
- We have to minimize single points of failure in the system. This leads us to choose a share-nothing architecture.
- System components have to be **responsive** (respond in a timely manner, focused on providing rapid and consistent response time), **resilient** (responsive in the face of failure), **elastic** (stay responsive under varying workload, no central bottlenecks) and **message driven** (rely on asynchronous messaging that is also establishing boundaries between components). All these four presumptions are key demands of *Reactive Manifesto* [4]

The previously listed non-functional requirements that should be met by the implemented system, have motivated our decision to base our design on a *microservice architecture*, which presumes that each component can be characterized by the following properties: isolation, autonomy, single responsibility, exclusive state, asynchronous message passing and mobility [5]. Those properties are in line with the previously-listed key design requirements.

Figure 5 is showing the way we have designed and implemented microservices in Core Services and Cloud Domain areas.

We are basing our implementation on the *Spring* framework (*Spring Boot*, *Spring Cloud* [6]) that facilitates component configuration, services discovery (*Eureka* middle tier load balancer [7]) and tracing (*Zipkin* distributed tracing system [8]). It means we are using already existing and well-established standard, ready-to-use solutions everywhere where it is suitable and do not affect system business logic in a negative way.

As it was pointed out during the analysis phase, we decided to use asynchronous messaging inside the system. This kind of communication is one of the inherent features

of the microservice architecture. Without asynchronous messaging microservices cannot reach their full potential.

In our case the internal messaging system of choice is the AMQP [9] standard messaging protocol adopted by OASIS. We are using RabbitMQ [10] server and each separate component is implementing messaging solution using AMQP compliant framework such as RabbitMQ [10] or Spring AMQP [11]. Communication interfaces of each component are described in chapter 4. Examples of payload are available in Appendix. Outside interfaces, designed to be used by client applications and platforms, are RESTful and their definitions and use examples are also shown in Appendix.

4 First release components

This chapter provides detailed information about L1 components that are under the implementation process within Task 2.2. For each component, we are reporting the features, some already implemented within Release 1, while others are still in the design phase. We are reporting component's general description, information about interface and currently implemented features. YAML definition of REST interfaces and payload examples are included in the Appendix (see Chapter 9). Components are presented in the alphabetical order.

The examples of Release 1 software usage are shown in Appendix. Chapter 9.5 contains a detailed description of the platform L1 integration process from the IoT platform owner point of view – this is a practical guide showing how to attempt to achieve Level 1 of Compliance.

4.1 Component: Administration

4.1.1 Administration component description

This component facilitates the control and administration of the symbloTe Core Services by providing a web-based GUI. symbloTe administrators will have access to a control panel that allows them to perform management actions and update parameters related to the symbloTe Core Services.

The role of this component will be also to provide features to non-administrator users. It will enable IoT platforms and applications to register with symbloTe and to receive credentials that are required for the subsequent usage of symbloTe services.

In terms of the first release, Administration's main functionality is restricted to two scenarios:

- providing GUI and server-side logic for symbloTe user registration (e.g. IoT platform owner/administrator);
- providing GUI and server-side logic for manual IoT platform registration in symbloTe.

In current release Administration component (as all core symbloTe modules) communicates with Registry in an asynchronous manner.

4.1.2 Administration component interface

Administration is the only one component from the core services layer that have the exposed GUI part. Internally Administration is communicating only with core components, like the rest of them - via asynchronous communication. So besides GUI, we have also message driven interface for internal communication in Administration. The current set of the messages, their meaning, the component that acts as consumer and the payload is shown in the following table.

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ¹	Description
1	Platform Registration (RPC)	platform.creationRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	Event requesting creation of new platform
1a	RPC response	platform.creationPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform creation request
2	Platform modification (RPC)	platform.modificationRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique ID	Event requesting modification of existing platform.
2a	RPC response	platform.modificationPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform modification request
3	Platform removal (RPC)	platform.removalRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique ID	Event requesting removal of existing platform
3a	RPC response	platform.removalPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform removal request

¹ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.1.3 Current release features of Administration component

Administration component for current release has to allow manual registration of (through website interface) a new symbloTe user and new symbloTe platform. This implicates the following features:

- Web pages for:
 - symbloTe administrator / user login
 - form for user registration
 - form for platform registration
- Server-side logic for the above-listed web pages/forms implementing component's internal interface described in 4.1.2

4.2 Component: Cloud-Core Interface

4.2.1 Cloud-Core Interface description

Cloud-Core Interface is working as a gateway created for accessing symbloTe Core Services from the side of supported IoT platforms and symbloTe related platform-side components. In other words, it provides endpoints for all elements gathered in the Cloud Domain layer of symbloTe (as it is described in [1]) that need access to the symbloTe Core Services [1].

4.2.2 Cloud-Core Interface component interface

For needs of the current release, the outside API of this component is a set of REST endpoints. This is visible from IoT platforms and their supporting symbloTe elements. The internal communication inside the Core Services is event driven and is implemented using RabbitMQ. In the following releases we will include an implementation of an endpoint receiving RDF descriptions between the core and cloud layers. The current REST interface of Cloud-Core Interface is defined in Appendix in YAML format.

4.2.3 Current release features of Cloud-Core Interface

As mentioned before, the current release is not meant to operate on data in RDF format; therefore all services only accept resource descriptions supplied in JSON format. The currently supported operations include creating, modifying and deleting resources. Services work in a standard, blocking REST manner, therefore Cloud-Core Interface needs on one side to coordinate synchronous communication with clients and on the other side asynchronous handling of request with the core components.

4.3 Component: Core Interface

4.3.1 Core Interface description

Core Interface is a core northbound API for accessing symbloTe main core services by third parties. It defines a way of interaction for users and outer clients (i.e. applications and enablers) and plays the role of an I/O gateway to the symbloTe instance of Core Services.

4.3.2 Core Interface component interface

Similarly to Cloud-Core Interface, Core Interface acts as a gateway, allowing access to asynchronously connected core modules on the symbloTe side by opening standard REST endpoints to third parties. The current REST interface of Core Interface is supplied in Appendix in YAML format.

4.3.3 Current release features of Core Interface component

In the first release, Core Interface provides access to the Search module, allowing querying for registered resources using multiple parameters, e.g., resource location or its observed properties. In a future release, an endpoint for serving standard SPARQL queries is planned to be added as well.

Apart from querying registered resources, Core Interface provides access to Core Resource Access Monitor, which allows clients to obtain URLs for the resources on the platform side which they would like to access (i.e., a URL of Interworking Interface registered for a specific resource).

4.4 Component: Core Resource Access Monitor

4.4.1 Core Resource Access Monitor description

Core Resource Access Monitor (CRAM) acts as a proxy that redirects applications and enablers to the actual resources offered by symbloTe-enabled platforms. It must keep track of the resources assigned to applications/enablers in order to maintain resource popularity information within the Core Services. Such information is vital to mark resources with exclusive rights as unavailable, enable prioritized access to resources, and may be useful to estimate resource load. Specifically, CRAM must grant exclusive use of IoT resources, for underlying IoT platforms that support such a feature. Thus, it will not redirect applications and enablers to resources if their availability and the potentially associated QoS cannot be guaranteed by the underlying IoT platforms. It should also enable the prioritized access to IoT services if the underlying IoT platforms support prioritization. Furthermore, it should control the access to the advertised IoT services for reasons related to local legislation, current overload, security issues, etc., providing that the underlying IoT platforms offer such functionality. Finally, it may be able to make reservations of registered resources at the underlying IoT platforms and enablers supporting such a feature.

4.4.2 Core Resource Access Monitor interfaces

The Core Access Monitor does not expose any REST interfaces. It only communicates with the other core components by using RabbitMQ. Any need for inter-domain communication, either with applications, or with platform components, is facilitated by the Core Interface and the Cloud-Core Interface respectively via RabbitMQ too. In the table below, it is possible to see a summary of CRAM's interfaces.

#	Interface	Name	Msg Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ²	Description
1	Platform Created	symbloTe.platform.created	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	A new platform was added in the symbloTe system
2	Platform Updated	symbloTe.platform.updated	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	A platform was updated
3	Platform Deleted	symbloTe.platform.deleted	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform Id	A platform was deleted
4	Resource Created	symbloTe.resource.created	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Information	A new resource was added in the symbloTe system
5	Resource Updated	symbloTe.resource. updated	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Information	A resource was updated
6	Resource Deleted	symbloTe.resource.deleted	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Id	A resource was deleted
7	ChooseResInterface	symbloTe.CoreInterface. CoreResourceAccessMonitor.update_status	Event	CRAM	Application (via Core Interface)	Exchange: symbiote.CoreInterface, routing key equal to "Name" column	resource ID, state, core token, attributes in core	Inform the application for resource status updates
8	ChooseResInterface	symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor. .coreAPI.get_resource_urls	Event	Application (via Core Interface)	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor, routing key equal to "Name" column	resource IDs, foreign token, attributes in IoT platform	The application requests the resources urls
9	ReportUsageInterface	symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor .coreAPI.resource_usage	Event	RAP (via CloudCore Interface)	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor, routing key equal to "Name" column	resource IDs, usage status	Rap asynchronously emits resource usage per use/per stream start
10	ReportUsageInterface	symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor .coreAPI.resource_usage_ended	Event	RAP (via CloudCore Interface)	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor, routing key equal to "Name" column	resource IDs	Rap reports that the resource usage ended

² Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

11	ReportUsageInterface	symbiote.CoreResourceAccessMonitor .coreAPI.usage_report	Event	Cloud Monitoring (via CloudCore Interface)	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote. CoreResourceAccessMonitor, routing key equal to "Name" column	report, core token, attributes in core	Cloud Monitoring sends a usage report to CRAM
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4.4.3 Current release features of Core Resource Access Monitor

CRAM for current release has to allow applications/enablers to access resources by getting a list of resource ids and providing their URLs. This implies that CRAM has to offer:

- interfaces to listen for platform/resource events (e.g. creation, modification and deletion)
- an interface to listen for resource URL requests from the applications via the Core Interface
- logic to enable the retrieval of resource URLs from the CRAM's local database providing their ids.

4.5 Component: Core Resource Monitor

This component must monitor the availability of registered resources to regularly update resource status (online/offline/unavailable) maintained by the Registry. This will ensure that symbloTe search results do not contain resources if their availability cannot be guaranteed, e.g., IoT service types with exclusive access rights (e.g., actuators) are marked unavailable if being used and will thus not appear in search results. It uses scheduled tasks to check resource status. Either resource registrations or application-generated monitoring requests can trigger the scheduling of a monitoring task per resource (or a group of resources).

The component needs to provide appropriate credentials when checking resource status. In addition, it should monitor the load on the registered resources, either in a push or pull style, if IoT platforms and enablers support such functionality. The component may perform functional performance tests on registered resources.

The work related to Core Resource Monitor in Release 1 was conceptual, no implementation exists at the moment.

4.6 Component: Interworking Interface

4.6.1 Interworking Interface description

Interworking Interface acts as a gateway for allowing the communication of symbloTe platform components with the external world (i.e. applications or symbloTe core). Therefore, it simply forwards messages from the external world to the symbloTe components extending existing platforms and vice versa. It can also act as load balancer when multiple instances of the same platform component are instantiated (e.g. multiple Resource Access Proxy instances).

4.6.2 Interfaces

Interworking Interface exposes REST interfaces in the place of symbloTe platform component, so that they are reachable from the external world. It also implements RabbitMQ interfaces to communicate with other platform components. Furthermore, if a platform component wants to communicate with the external world, it has first to send the

request to the Interworking Interface via RabbitMQ, which is then forwarded to the external world via REST. The reply message from the external world follows the reverse flow. The table below presents the interfaces implemented in the current release:

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ³	Description
1	ReadResource		GET	Application/Enabler	RAP (via Interworking Interface)	/rap/Sensor('{resourceId}')		Get the current value of a resource
2	ReadResourceHistory		GET	Application/Enabler	RAP (via Interworking Interface)	/rap/Sensor('{resourceId}')/history		Get historical value of the resource
3	WriteResource		POST	Application/Enabler	RAP (via Interworking Interface)	/rap/Resource('{resourceId}')	Value to be written provided as a simple string in the payload	Used to write a value to a resource (e.g. actuator)
4	resourceRegistration	symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.register_resources	Spring AMQP RPC	Registration Handler	Registry (via Interworking Interface and CloudCoreAPI)	Exchange: symbiote. resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Information	A new resource to be added in the symbloTe system
5	resourceUnregistration	symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.unregister_resources	Spring AMQP RPC	Registration Handler	Registry (via Interworking Interface and CloudCoreAPI)	Exchange: symbiote. resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Information	A resource to be updated
6	resourceUpdate	symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.update_resources	Spring AMQP RPC	Registration Handler	Registry (via Interworking Interface and CloudCoreAPI)	Exchange: symbiote. resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Id	A resource to be deleted

³ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.6.3 Current release features of Interworking Interface

In the current release, Interworking interface has to allow the communication of Registration Handler and Resource Access Proxy with entities outside the Cloud Domain. Thus, in the current release it has to offer:

- REST interfaces for listening to requests targeting Resource Access Proxy and forwarding them to it
- Spring AMQP interfaces for listening to Registration Handler requests and forwarding them to the symbloTe core

4.7 Component: Monitoring

This component is responsible for two different tasks: monitoring the status of resources and monitoring the access to resources from applications/enablers.

The component will monitor periodically the status of the resources that are being exposed to symbloTe Core Services. It will receive the IDs of the resources that must be monitored. These ids can belong to IoT resources. The information from the Monitoring will be forwarded to the Resource Monitor residing in the symbloTe Core Services.

The work related to Monitoring in Release 1 was conceptual, no implementation is existing at the moment. The foreseen interfaces from this component with the RAP and Registration handler are the following:

#	Interface	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue/Exchange type	Payload ⁴	Description
1	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.register_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
2	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.unregister_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
3	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.update_resources Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource

4.8 Component: Registration Handler

This component will drive an IoT Platform Provider through the step of registering resources into the symbloTe Core. Registration Handler needs to provide the following information from the symbloTe information model: IoT Device or Composite IoT Service description, Location with its properties, Observed Properties description and name.

Registration Handler will send the metadata describing resources to be registered to the Interworking Interface that will communicate with the Registry. Registry accepts the

⁴ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

registration requests, and replies to the Registration Handler (through interworking interface) with a list of IDs generated by symbloTe Core Services for those resources. A similar process is occurring in the case of unregistration of a resource or update of the resource information. Both processes can be triggered by the Registration Handler.

The IoT Platform Provider must be able to define which of its resources are available to use, and under which conditions. A platform does not have to expose all of its resources to symbloTe. Instead, they may opt to reveal just a subset.

The foreseen interfaces from this component with the Interworking Interface, RAP and monitoring are shown in the following table.

#	Interface	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue/Exchange type	Payload ⁵	Description
1	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	INTERWOKING INTERFACE	Exchange: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface routing key: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.register_resources Routing type: RPC	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
2	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	INTERWOKING INTERFACE	Exchange: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface routing key: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.unregister_resources Routing type: RPC	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
3	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	INTERWOKING INTERFACE	Exchange: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface routing key: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.update_resources Routing type: RPC	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
4	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.rap.register_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
5	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.rap.unregister_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
6	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.rap.update_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
7	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.register_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
8	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.unregister_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
9	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.update_resources Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource

⁵ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.9 Component: Registry

4.9.1 Registry component description

This component handles registration of symbloTe actors, i.e. users, platforms and resources. After registering, IoT platforms can add their resources that they want to make discoverable via symbloTe.

The component provides unique symbloTe identifiers to all resources registered within the symbloTe Core Services. Uniqueness is enforced both within and across IoT platform boundaries, which is critical, e.g., in the case of roaming IoT devices.

Registry module is a part of symbloTe Core Services. It communicates with other modules using asynchronous, event driven scheme.

4.9.2 Registry component interface

As Registry is strictly a core module, the only communication it supports is via RabbitMQ asynchronous messaging. Its interface, based on asynchronous exchanges and routing keys, is described in the following table.

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁶	Description
1	Platform Registration (RPC)	platform.creationRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	Event requesting creation of new platform
1a	RPC response	platform.creationPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform creation request
1b	Message	platform.created	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that new platform has been successfully created in database.
2	Platform modification (RPC)	platform.modificationRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique ID	Event requesting modification of existing platform.
2a	RPC response	platform.modificationPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform modification request
2b	Message	platform.modified	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that platform description has been successfully changed.
3	Platform removal (RPC)	platform.removalRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique ID	Event requesting removal of existing platform
3a	RPC response	platform.removalPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform removal request
3b	Message	platform.removed	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that platform with specified id has been deleted from the repository
4	Resource Registration (RPC)	resource.creationRequested	event	Cloud-Core Interface	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information	Event requesting creation of new resource

⁶ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4a	RPC response	resource.creationPerformed	event	Registry	Cloud-Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Resource information	Response to the RPC resource creation request
4b	Message	resource.created	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique id	Event informing that new resource has been successfully created in database.
5	Resource modification (RPC)	resource.modificationRequested	event	Cloud-Core Interface	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique ID	Event requesting modification of existing resource.
5a	RPC response	resource.modificationPerformed	event	Registry	Cloud-Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Resource information	Response to the RPC resource modification request
5b	Message	resource.modified	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique id	Event informing that resource description has been successfully changed.
6	Resource removal (RPC)	resource.removalRequested	event	Cloud-Core Interface	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique ID	Event requesting removal of existing resource
6a	RPC response	resource.removalPerformed	event	Registry	Cloud-Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Resource information	Response to the RPC resource removal request
6b	Message	resource.removed	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique id	Event informing that resource with specified id has been deleted from the repository

4.9.3 Current release features of Registry component

For the current release, Registry component manages to fulfill its basic tasks, which is registering, modifying and removing platforms and resources. It uses no-SQL Mongo DB for its storage. The communication protocol is also established, so that other modules can be notified of performed tasks.

Registry uses basic JSON format to describe both platforms and resources.

4.10 Component: Resource Access Proxy

This component enables symbloTe-compliant access to resources within an IoT platform (or enabler acting as a platform).

It must receive incoming access requests from applications/enablers using a symbloTe-compliant communication protocol and data format. A request must contain a unique identifier assigned to a resource. It must check that a token included in the request is valid and that access to a particular resource can be granted.

The data generated by IoT platform must be returned in a format which complies with the symbloTe information model.

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁷	Description
1	Resource registration	symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.register_resources	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.rap Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
2	Resource registration	symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.unregister_resources	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.rap Routing key: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
3	Resource registration	symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.update_resources	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.rap Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
4	Resource access read	/rap/Sensor({resourceId})	REST	Interworking Interface	RAP	GET	None - replies with the value of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource
5	Resource access read history	/rap/Sensor({resourceId}/history	REST	Interworking Interface	RAP	GET	None - replies with the history values of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource Not handled in Release 1
6	Resource access write	/rap/Resource({resourceId})	REST	Interworking Interface	RAP	POST	The value to write into the resource	Event writing the value of a resource Not handled in Release 1

⁷ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.11 Component: Search

4.11.1 Search component description

This component allows developers of applications and enablers to search for resources available through symbloTe Core Service. Search requests specify a set of query parameters which are used to create SPARQL query and perform search operation and find relevant resources.

To provide the search functionality this component stores the representations of the objects registered by symbloTe Core (such as platforms and their resources) in Apache Jena. Translation into RDF statements (compliant with current version of information models: MIM and CIM) is done within the component and is triggered by event created by the Registry component.

4.11.2 Search component interface

Search communicates with other modules using asynchronous messaging based on RabbitMQ AMQP implementation. Its interface, based on asynchronous exchanges and routing keys, is described in the following table.

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁸	Description
1	Platform creation	platform.created	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that new platform has been successfully created in repository.
2	Platform modification	platform.modified	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that platform has been successfully modified in repository.
3	Platform removal	platform.removed	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that platform has been successfully removed from repository.
4	Resource creation	resource.created	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including platform unique id	Event informing that new resource has been successfully created in repository.
5	Resource modification	resource.modified	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including platform unique id	Event informing that resource has been successfully modified in repository.
6	Resource removal	resource.removed	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including platform unique id	Event informing that resource has been successfully removed from repository.
7	Resource query (RPC)	resource.searchRequested	event	Core Interface	Search	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Query parameters	Event requesting query results for supplied query parameters
7a	RPC response	resource.searchPerformed	event	Search	Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Search Response	Query results, containing resources matching specified parameters

⁸ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.11.3 Current release features of Search component

Current release of the Search is based on Apache Jena. It's features consist of: translation of the Resource and Platform payload objects (see Appendix 9.3) into their representations compliant with a subset of Meta Information Model v0.2 and Core Information Model v0.5.

Search is also providing translation of the parameterized query into SPARQL and ability to perform the search and return information about found resources as a SearchResponse (see Appendix 9.3).

Search is integrated with event messaging:

- Registry component triggers translation and storage of the Resource and Platform RDF representations in Search. Handling of the removal and update of those resources is also performed using SPARQL Update extension to the SPARQL language.
- Core Interface component triggers search parameters translation into SPARQL and performing the search for the resources fitting the criteria. Information about found resources is collected and send back to the client.

5 Components / services basic information tables

This chapter contains all basic information about symbloTe system components implemented for the first release. We gathered it in form of tables, one per each module (or / and service). Components are presented in alphabetical order.

5.1 Administration

Component/service name	Administration
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Administration
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/Administration/doxygen/
List of 1 st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented manual (through website) user registration supported manual (through website) IoT platform registration and removal supported

5.2 Cloud-Core Interface

Component/service name	Cloud-Core Interface
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CloudCoreInterface
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CloudCoreInterface/doxygen/
List of 1 st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REST endpoints for Registration Handler requests implemented asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to publish messages to other components)

5.3 Core Interface

Component/service name	Core Interface
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CoreInterface
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CoreInterface/doxygen/
List of 1 st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> synchronous REST endpoint for receiving parametrized queries from end-user applications and responding with list of resources implemented asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to proxy queries to Search component and receiving results)

5.4 Core Resource Access Monitor

Component/service name	Core Resource Access Monitor
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CoreResourceAccessMonitor
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CoreResourceAccessMonitor/doxygen/
List of 1st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interfaces for listening to platform/resource events redirection to actual resources by providing the resource urls to the applications (via the CoreInterface)

5.5 Interworking Interface

Component/service name	Interworking Interface
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/InterworkingInterface
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/InterworkingInterface/doxygen/
List of 1st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REST Interfaces for allowing access to the RAP asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interfaces for listening and forwarding the Registration Handler's resource requests (i.e. resource creation/modification/update) to the symbloTe core

5.6 Monitoring

Component/service name	Monitoring
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Monitoring
URL of working service	Not published. Under development.
URL of Javadoc documentation	Not published
List of 1st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Icinga2 server has been installed in a public machine in order to enable test by partners without the need of installing Icinga2.

5.7 Registration Handler

Component/service name	Registration Handler
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/RegistrationHandler
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/RegistrationHandler/doxygen/
List of 1st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rest interfaces has been implemented Storage in <i>mongo db</i> is being done messaging (AMQP) has been implemented. They you

	communicate using the RPC RabbitMQ communication pattern with Interworking Interface and Routing-direct RabbitMQ communication pattern with RAP component.
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5.8 Registry

Component/service name	Registry
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Registry
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/Registry/doxygen/
List of 1 st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to receive event messages from Administration component and publish messages to other components) Platform, Resource and Location persistence layer implemented providing a unique ID for every registered object supported creation, modification and removal of Platform/Resource (delivered via AMQP message) supported

5.9 Resource Access Proxy

Component/service name	Resource Access Proxy
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/ResourceAccessProxy
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/RegistrationHandler/doxygen/
List of 1 st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to receive registration messages from Resource Handler) Internal storage of Platform and Resource IDs mapping translating Platform and Resource IDs to forward requests to IoT platforms REST endpoint for access to resources Internal asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to decouple generic rap features from platforms' proprietary access to resources)

5.10 Search

Component/service name	Search
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Search
URL of working service	Not published, development version deployed in Release 1
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/Search/doxygen/
List of 1 st release features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to receive event messages from Registry and queries from

	<p>Core Interface)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• translating and saving Platforms and Resources in triplets store (JENA) implemented (RDFs in compliance with CIM and MIM supported)• AMQP endpoint for receiving and translating parameterized queries into SPARQL implemented• querying the JENA database with SPARQL query and creating JSON response containing resource information implemented
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6 Conclusions and next steps

The current document is a report from the first period of work related with symbloTe middleware software. The main outcome of this work at the current stage is the source code and its documentation, published as an open source project in the GitHub service: <https://github.com/symbiote-h2020>

There are 9 main software components implemented included in Release 1, 4 stub projects and several 6 supporting projects with separate repositories – all gathered in two GitHub super-projects: *SymbioteCore* and *SymbioteCloud*.

The main implemented modules are: *Administration*, *Cloud-Core Interface*, *Core Interface*, *Core Resource Access Monitor*, *Registry*, *Search*, *Interworking Interface*, *Registration Handler* and *Resource Access Proxy*.

The supporting projects are: *CoreConfigService*, *CloudConfigService* and two versions (core and cloud) of *EurekaService* and *ZipkinService*.

Not implemented yet stubs are: *Core Authentication and Authorization Module*, *Core Resource Monitor*, *Monitoring* and *Cloud Access and Authorization Module* (will be renamed to *Platform AAM* in Release 2)

The symbloTe software is under development - we just finished Release 1 and components functionalities will be extended in next two releases planned for:

- Release 2 by the end of April 2017
- Release 3 by the end of June 2017

The next step in expanding project capabilities will be introducing four new components predicted in architecture related conceptual work: *Core Authentication and Authorization Module (CAAM)*, *Platform Authentication and Authorization Module (PAAM* – previously named *Cloud AAM*), *Security Handler* and *Monitoring*. It means that one of the main goals of Release 2 (and 3 also) will be introduction of security mechanisms – first 3 components mentioned are strictly related to this topic. *Monitoring* is a tracking module by IoT platform side cooperating with *Core Resource Monitor* in core layer in terms of platforms' resources status, availability, load and usage tracking.

Of course, beside new components, there is a plan for continuous and incremental work on upgrading functionality of already existing system modules. They have essential part of functionality included in Release 1, but there are also a lot of features yet to be addressed and implemented in following months for Release 2 and 3.

7 Definitions, acronyms, abbreviations

AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Best Practice Information Model
CIM	Core Information Model
CRAM	Core Resource Access Monitor, one of symbloTe core software components
ID	Identifier
IM	Information Model
IoT	Internet of Things
JENA	Free and open source Java framework for building Semantic Web and Linked Data applications
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON-based Serialization for Linked Data
L1	Level 1 of Compliance – symbloTe compliance level related to Application and Cloud domains
MIM	Meta Information Model
PIM	Platform-Specific Information Model
QoS	Quality of Service
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFa	Resource Description Framework in Attributes
RDFS	RDF Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
symbloTe	Symbiosis of Smart Objects across IoT Environments
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

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9 Appendix – interfaces definitions, communication messages payloads and examples

9.1 Cloud-Core Interface – Swagger (YAML) representation of API and payload

```
swagger: '2.0'
info:
  version: "1.0"
  title: Cloud Core Interface
schemes:
  - http
host: symbiote.man.poznan.pl
basePath: /cloudCoreInterface/v1
paths:

  /platforms/{platformId}/resources:
    post:
      summary: Create resource using JSON format
      parameters:
        - $ref: "#/parameters/platformId"
        - name: resource
          in: body
          required: true
          description: Resource to add (without id field set)
          schema:
            $ref: "#/definitions/Resource"
      responses:
        200:
          description: Resource created successfully
          schema:
            $ref: "#/definitions/Resource"

        400:
          description: Bad request format

        500:
          description: Error while creating resource on server side
```

```
/platforms/{platformId}/resources/{id}:
  put:
    summary: Modify specified resource
    parameters:
      - $ref: "#/parameters/platformId"
      - $ref: "#/parameters/id"
      - name: resource
        in: body
    description: resource to modify (without id field set)
    required: true
    schema:
      $ref: "#/definitions/Resource"
    responses:
      200:
        description: Resource modified successfully
      400:
        description: Bad request format
      500:
        description: Error while modifying resource on server side
  delete:
    summary: Delete specified resource
    parameters:
      - $ref: "#/parameters/platformId"
      - $ref: "#/parameters/id"
    responses:
      200:
        description: A resource object in RDF format
      400:
        description: Bad request format
      500:
        description: Error while deleting resource on server side

definitions:
  Location:
    properties:
      id:
        type: string
      name:
        type: string
      description:
        type: string
```

```
latitude:
  type: number
  format: double
longitude:
  type: number
  format: double
altitude:
  type: number
  format: double
```

Resource:

```
properties:
  id:
    type: string
  name:
    type: string
  owner:
    type: string
  description:
    type: string
  observedProperties:
    type: array
    items:
      type: string
  resourceURL:
    type: string
  location:
    $ref: "#/definitions/Location"
  featureOfInterest:
    type: string
```

parameters:

```
id:
  name: id
  in: path
  required: true
  description: id of a resource
  type: string
platformId:
  name: platformId
  in: path
```

```
required: true  
description: id of a platform  
type: string
```

9.2 Core Interface – Swagger (YAML) representation of API and payload

```
swagger: '2.0'
info:
  version: "1.0"
  title: Core Interface
schemes:
  - http
host: symbiote.man.poznan.pl
basePath: /coreInterface/v1
paths:
  /query:
    get:
      summary: Search for resources using query parameters
      parameters:
        - name: platform_id
          in: query
          required: false
          type: string
        - name: platform_name
          in: query
          required: false
          type: string
        - name: owner
          in: query
          required: false
          type: string
        - name: name
          in: query
          required: false
          type: string
        - name: id
          in: query
          required: false
          type: string
        - name: description
          in: query
          required: false
          type: string
        - name: location_name
```

```
    in: query
    required: false
    type: string
  - name: location_lat
    in: query
    required: false
    type: number
    format: double
  - name: location_long
    in: query
    required: false
    type: number
    format: double
  - name: max_distance
    in: query
    required: false
    type: integer
  - name: observed_property
    in: query
    required: false
    type: string
    description: can be passed multiple times (acts as AND)
responses:
  200:
    description: Query executed successfully
    schema:
      $ref: "#/definitions/ResourceList"
  500:
    description: Query execution error on server side

/resourceUrls:
get:
  summary: Gets URLs of resource specified by passed IDs
  parameters:
    - name: id
      in: query
      required: true
      type: string
      description: can be passed multiple times to serve multiple resources
  responses:
    200:
```

```
description: Request served succesfully
schema:
  description: Map containing "id" - "URL" pairs
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
500:
  description: Error on server side
```

definitions:

Resource:

```
properties:
  id:
    type: string
  name:
    type: string
  owner:
    type: string
  platformId:
    type: string
  platformName:
    type: string
  locationName:
    type: string
  locationLatitude:
    type: number
    format: double
  locationLongitude:
    type: number
    format: double
  locationAltitude:
    type: number
    format: double
  observedProperties:
    type: array
    items:
      type: string
```

ResourceList:

```
type: array
```

items:

\$ref: "#/definitions/Resource"

9.3 Payload definitions

9.3.1 Core side payload definitions

9.3.1.1 Platform

Describes the platform in Core communication. Contains the symbloTe-generated unique id of the platform (*platformId*), as well as information about the platform, which is provided using the Admin component.

```
Platform {
    platformId:      String
    name:           String
    description:    String
    url:           String
    informationModelId: String
}
```

9.3.1.2 Resource

Describes the resource in Core communication. Contains the unique symbloTe-generated id of the resource (*id*), information about the resource (*name*, *owner* and *description*), list of properties observed by this resource (*observedProperties*), base access URL of the resource (*resourceURL* – should point to the *Interworking Interface* that handles this particular resource), resource's location (*location*), feature of interest for the resource (*featureOfInterest*) and the id of the platform this resource belongs to (*platformId*).

```
Resource {
    id:           String
    name:        String
    owner:       String
    description: String
    observedProperties: List<String>
    resourceURL: String
    location:    Location
    featureOfInterest String
    platformId: String
}
```

9.3.1.3 Location

Object representing location of the resource. Contains unique symbloTe-generated id of the Location (*id*), name and description of the location and geo-parameters of the location.

```
Location {
    id:                String
    name:              String
    description:       String
    latitude:          Double
    longitude:         Double
    altitude:          Double
}
```

9.3.1.4 Search parameters

Following payload contains a list of optional parameters that can be used in the *HTTP GET* query string to search for resources advertised in symbloTe using *REST* endpoint of the *CoreInterface*. Possible search parameters include: platform info (it's id, name and owner), resource info (it's id, name and description), location resource is located in (using location name and/or distance from particular location) as well as list of observed properties by the resource.

```
Query parameters {
    platform_id:       String
    platform_name:    String
    owner:            String
    name:             String
    id:              String
    description:      String
    location_name:    String
    location_lat:     Double
    location_long:    Double
    max_distance:     Integer
    observed_property: List<String>
}
```

9.3.1.5 Search response

This payload represents single answer to the search query (search query returns list of *ResponseResources*). Response correlates strictly to internal *Core Resource* payload from point 9.3.1.2, with main differences being: access URL of the resource is omitted from this response (granting access link to the resource is done using *resourceUrls* endpoint of Cloud Interface) and resource location is represented in the flat JSON

representation (instead of nested *Location* object). Also not only id of the platform that found resource belongs to is returned, but also its name.

```
ResponseResource {
    id:                String
    name:              String
    description:       String
    platformId:        String
    platformName:      String
    locationName:      String
    locationLatitude:  Double
    locationLongitude: Double
    locationAltitude: Double
    observedProperty: List<String>
}
```

9.3.2 Cloud side payload definitions

9.3.2.1 *ResourceBean*

This resource definition differs slightly from Core *Resource* definition. It is used to describe resource on the Cloud side and is used for example to send a registration request to *Registration Handler*. It contains an internal id of the resource on the Cloud side (*internalId*) as well as symbloTe-generated id for the resource (*id*). The internal id is never shared outside of the Cloud side of the symbloTe.

```
ResourceBean {
    internalId:        String
    id:                String
    name:              String
    owner:             String
    description:       String
    location:          LocationBean
    observedProperties: List<String>
    resourceURL:       String
}
```

9.3.2.2 *LocationBean*

This payload represents a location of the resource.

```
LocationBean {
    name:              String
```

Public

```
description:      String
longitude:       Double
latitude:       Double
altitude        Double
}
```

9.4 Examples

Below you can find examples of how to use various components of symbloTe. It assumes components are properly setup and running on following addresses:

- *Admin GUI* <http://core.symbiote.eu:8250>
- *Cloud Core Interface* <http://core.symbiote.eu:8101/cloudCoreInterface/v1/>
- *Core Interface* <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/>
- *Registration Handler* <http://myplatform.eu:8001/>
- *Interworking Interface* <http://myplatform.eu:8101/>
- *Resource Access Proxy* <http://myplatform.eu:8100/rap>
<http://myplatform.eu:8101/>

Examples below are assuming addresses relative to this exemplary addresses.

9.4.1 Registration and configuration of the platform

Use the *Admin GUI* to register new user and create new platform with specified description. After registration is complete you will receive unique Id for your platform.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Register Platform". It has four input fields and a button:

- Name:** PlatformA
- Description:** This is a test Platform A
- Url:** http://myplatform.eu:8101/
- Information Model:** 1
- Register** button

Figure 8 Platform registration in Administration module GUI

9.4.2 Configuration of the symbloTe Cloud

Configuration that needs to be done on the platform side. It is done in file *application.properties* of platforms *CloudConfigProperties*. Platform.id for configuration is retrieved from the *Admin GUI*.

```
symbIoTe.core.url=http://core.symbiote.eu:8101/cloudCoreInterface/v1/  
platform.id=589c783a9bddd2d2a7f3a92  
rap.url=http://myplatform.eu:8100/
```

9.4.3 Resource registration

Registers the resource in the symbloTe Core and sends the messages about the received unique resource id between symbloTe Cloud components.

POST on <http://myplatform.eu:8001/resource>

Payload:

```
{  
  "name": "Sensor1",  
  "owner": "PlatformAOwner",  
  "description": "This is a test sensor",  
  "resourceURL" : "http://myplatform.eu:8101/rap/",  
  "internalId": "Sensor1",  
  "location":  
    {  
      "name": "Poznan",  
      "description": "Poznan - malta",  
      "longitude": 18.940144,  
      "latitude": 54.421790,  
      "altitude": 100.0  
    },  
  "observedProperties":  
    [  
      "Temperature"  
    ]  
}
```

9.4.4 Search for resources

Searches the resources registered in symbloTe Core fulfilling specified criteria. List of possible query parameters are described in 9.3 *Query parameters*.

All examples are send using **HTTP GET** on

<http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/query>

with following example parameters used in a standard HTTP GET query string way:

- Search for resources which name starts with Sensor
?name=Sensor*
- Search for resources which contains “1” in their name
?name=*1*
- Search for resources in 100 meter distance around point Lat 54.421790, Long 18.940144
?location_lat=54.421790&location_long=18.940144&max_distance=100

9.5 Description of L1 Integration process

This paragraph contains a detailed description of the platform L1 integration process. As a result of the following steps you will setup and run symbloTe Cloud components for your platform. You will also register your platform and resources in symbloTe Core offered by symbloTe project, which collects the metadata for all symbloTe-enabled platforms. This will allow other symbloTe users to use the Core to search and access resources that have been shared by you.

9.5.1 Preparation steps

9.5.1.1 Installation of required tools for symbloTe platform components

Platform components require the following tools to be installed:

- [RabbitMQ](#) - message queue server for internal messaging between platform components
- [MongoDB](#) - database used by Registration Handler and Interworking Interface
- [MySQL](#) - database used by Resource Access Proxy (will be changed to MongoDB in Release 2)

Besides that platform owner will need to provide a Java implementation of the platform-specific access to to the resources and their readings (observations). So some IDE for write code and [Gradle](#) version 3+ for building and running of the components is required.

9.5.1.2 Download symbloTe platform components

Platform components are available in the github, bundled in the following directory: <https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SymbioteCloud>. Master branches contains latest stable symbloTe release version (starting from release 1), develop branch is a general development branch containing newest features that are added during development and

particular feature branches where features are developed. For symbloTe cloud installation, following components are currently used and required to properly start platform in L1 compliance:

- CloudConfigService - service that distributes configuration among platform components
- EurekaService - allows discovery of platform components
- ZipkinService - collects logs from various services
- InterworkingInterface (abbr. *I/I*) - is used to forward communication from platform components to symbloTe Core
- RegistrationHandler (abbr. *RH*) - service responsible for properly registering platform's resources and distribute this information among platform components
- ResourceAccessProxy (abbr. *RAP*) - service responsible for providing access to the real readings of the platform's resources

There is also another project that needs to be downloaded and set up properly, containing configuration of the symbloTe Cloud components, which can be found in <https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CloudConfigProperties>

- CloudConfigProperties - contains a list of properties to configure platform components.
It must be either deployed in `$HOME/git/symbiote/CloudConfigProperties` or property `spring.cloud.config.server.git.uri` must be properly set in `src/main/resources/bootstrap.properties` of `CloudConfigService` component.

For the example integration process described below we assume the following addresses of various Core and Cloud components:

- *Admin GUI* <http://core.symbiote.eu:8250>
- *Cloud Core Interface* <http://core.symbiote.eu:8101/cloudCoreInterface/v1/>
- *Core Interface* <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/>
- *Registration Handler* <http://myplatform.eu:8001/>
- *Interworking Interface* <http://myplatform.eu:8101/>
- *Resource Access Proxy* <http://myplatform.eu:8100/>

9.5.2 Integration with symbloTe

9.5.2.1 Provide platform-specific access to the resource and data

Platform owner needs to extend `PlatformSpecificPlugin` class of the `ResourceAccessProxy`. Method that needs to be extended is `readResource`, accepting `resourceId` (id of the resource that is used to identify the resource internally within a platform). Method must return a simple POJO object containing the current value of the resource with specified `resourceId`.

```
public Observation readResource(String resourceId) {
    Observation value = null;
    //
    // INSERT HERE: query to the platform with internal resource id
    //
    return value;
}
```

Example of the implementation returning just a simple value can be seen below.

```
public Observation readResource(String resourceId) {
    Observation value = null;
    System.out.println("Reading resource");

    String sensorId = "symbIoTeID1";

    WGS84Location loc = new WGS84Location(16.940144, 52.42179, 100,
        "Poznan", "Poznan test");

    long timestamp = System.currentTimeMillis();

    ObservationValue obsval = new ObservationValue((double)7,
        new Property("Temperature", "Air temperature"),
        new UnitOfMeasurement("C", "degree Celsius", ""));
    value = new Observation(sensorId, loc, timestamp, timestamp-1000, obsval);

    return value;
}
```

9.5.2.2 Register user and configure platform

The next step is to create a user in the symbloTe Core Admin webpage. After creating the user and registering, the user needs to specify the description of their platform (see Figure 8).

- Name - name of the platform
- Description - description of the platform
- Url - url of the platform's *Interworking Interface* which will provide entry point to symbloTe Cloud components. For the example we assume our platform's Interworking Interface is running on address <http://myplatform.eu:8101/>
- Information Model - used to differentiate between types of information models - to be used in the future when we provide support for platform specific information models.

After registration of the platform portal displays the unique **platformId** that we will use for configuration in the next step.

Figure 9 Platform id generated by symbloTe.

9.5.2.3 Configuration of the symbloTe Cloud components

Before starting symbloTe Cloud components we need to provide proper configuration in the *CloudConfigProperties* component. Please edit *application.properties* file contained in this component. Platform owner needs to provide URL address of the *CloudCoreInterface* and **platformId** of the platform we registered. It also provides address where RAP service is running:

```
symbIoTe.core.url=http://core.symbiote.eu:8101/cloudCoreInterface/v1/  
  
platform.id=58a5a85e9bddd4dfedb2495  
  
rap.url=http://myplatform.eu:8100/
```

RAP configuration is done in *ResourceAccessProxy* component itself - file *src/main/resources/bootstrap.properties* needs to be edited to provide MySQL database configuration:

```
# DataSource settings: set here your own configurations for the database  
# connection.  
  
spring.datasource.url = jdbc:mysql://localhost:3306/symbioterap  
spring.datasource.username = user  
spring.datasource.password = pass
```

Create the database in MySQL you specified in *application.properties* file (it will not be created on first deployment automatically).

9.5.2.4 Starting of the symbloTe Cloud components

Starting symbloTe Cloud components can be done in following steps:

1. Start RabbitMQ server
2. Start MongoDB server
3. Start MySQL server
4. Start symbloTe Cloud components
 - a. make sure to first start *CloudConfigService*, and after it is running start *EurekaService*
 - b. after both services are running you can start rest of the components: *ZipkinService*, *InterworkingInterface*, *ResourceHandler*, *ResourceAccessProxy*

To start Cloud components you can use *gradle bootRun* task.

9.5.2.5 Register resource

After our platform has been registered and symbloTe Cloud components for our platform are configured and running we can proceed to expose some of our platform's resources to

symbloTe Core. It is done by sending *HTTP POST* request containing resource description on *ResourceHandler's* registration endpoint. Exemplary description is shown below:

```
{
  "name": "Sensor1",
  "owner": "PlatformAOwner",
  "description": "This is a test sensor",
  "resourceURL" : "http://myplatform.eu:8101/",
  "internalId": "1234",
  "location":
  {
    "name": "Poznan",
    "description": "Poznan - malta",
    "longitude": 16.940144,
    "latitude": 52.421790,
    "altitude": 100.0
  },
  "observedProperties":
  [
    "Temperature"
  ]
}
```

Important note about the resource registration parameters

To register this sensor we *POST* it on our example setup's RH endpoint at <http://myplatform.eu:8001/resource>. RH uses II to communicate with symbloTe Core to register our platform's resource. If the registration process is successful Core returns resource containing field *symbioteld* with unique, generated id of the resource in the symbloTe Core layer. Information about the registered resource is distributed in Cloud components using RabbitMQ messaging.

9.5.3 Test integrated resource

After our resource have been shared with Core we can test if we can find and access it properly.

9.5.3.1 Search for resource

To search for resource we need to create a query to the symbloTe Core. In our example we use <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/query> endpoint and provide parameters for query. All possible query parameters can be found in the 9.3

NOTE1 To query using geospatial properties, all 3 properties need to be set: *location_lat* (latitude), *location_long* (longitude) and *max_distance* (distance from specified point in meters).

NOTE2 Text parameters allow substring searches using '*' character which can be placed at the beginning and/or end of the word to search for. For example querying for name: *Sensor** finds all resources with name starting with *Sensor*, and search for name: **12** will find all resources containing string "12" in its name. Using substring search can be done for the following fields:

- name
- platform_name
- owner
- description
- location_name
- observed_property

For our example lets search for resources with name *Sensor1*. We do it by sending *HTTP GET* on *symbloTe Core Interface*: <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/query?name=Sensor1>. *Response* contains a list of resources fulfilling the criteria:

```
[
  {
    "platformId": "589c783a9bddd2d2a7gea92",
    "platformName": "PlatformA",
    "owner": "PlatformAOwner",
    "name": "Sensor1",
    "id": "589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8",
    "description": "This is a test sensor",
    "locationName": "Poznan",
    "locationLatitude": 52.42179,
    "locationLongitude": 16.940144,
    "locationAltitude": 100,
    "observedProperties": [
```

```

    "Temperature"
  ]
}
]

```

9.5.3.2 Obtaining resource access URL

To access the resource we need to ask symbloTe Core for the access link. To do so we need to send *HTTP GET* request on <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/resourceUrls?id=589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8>

If we provided correct id of the resource we will get response containing URL to access the resource:

```

{
  "589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8":
  "http://myplatform.eu:8101/rap/Sensor\('589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8'\)"
}

```

9.5.3.3 Accessing the resource and triggering fetching of our example data

Accessing the URL link we retrieved from the previous step calls Interworking Interface of our platform and forwards the access request to the RAP component. RAP searches for the resource with id specified in the URL and looks for internal resource id of this resource. Method we created in point 2.1 is called to retrieve value of the resource with internal id and observation is returned.

HTTP GET on [http://myplatform.eu:8101/rap/Sensor\('589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8'\)](http://myplatform.eu:8101/rap/Sensor('589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8')) results in following response:

```

{
  "headers": {
    "X-Application-Context": [
      "ResourceAccessProxy:8100"
    ],
    "Content-Type": [
      "application/json;charset=UTF-8"
    ],
    "Transfer-Encoding": [
      "chunked"
    ],
    "Date": [
      "Wed, 15 Feb 2017 14:12:49 GMT"
    ]
  },
  "body": {
    "resultTime": 1487167969540,
    "resourceId": "symbIoTeID1",
  }
}

```

```

"samplingTime": 1487167968540,
"location": {
  "longitude": 16.940144,
  "latitude": 52.42179,
  "altitude": 100,
  "name": "Poznan",
  "description": "Poznan test"
},
"obsValue": {
  "value": 7,
  "obsProperty": {
    "label": "Temperature",
    "comment": "Air temperature"
  },
  "uom": {
    "symbol": "C",
    "label": "degree Celsius",
    "comment": null
  }
},
"statusCode": "OK",
"statusCodeValue": 200
}

```

9.5.4 Alternative approach to provide L1 compliance

There also exists an alternative approach to provide L1 platform compliance. It's more lightweight in terms of amount of cloud components that must be downloaded and configured, but requires more manual coding to provide proper registration and handling of the resources. To follow this approach you only need to download the Resource Access Proxy component. For the example we will create a simple Java application that will register the resource in symbloTe Core and inform RAP about the new resource using RabbitMQ.

Here are the more detailed steps:

1. We write platform-specific implementation of RAP plugin (similar to point 9.5.2.1 from original description) where we provide `readResource(String platformResourceId)` implementation to access specific resource for observation value.
2. You register your platform using Admin GUI. Platform's URL should point in this case to where your RAP instance will be running directly.
3. Start MySQL and RAP instance.
4. We need to write some code that will register our resource in symbloTe Core, using HTTP POST `CloudCoreInterface` endpoint.
 - a. We need to create registration request. Simplest way is to create POJO object <https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CloudCoreInterface/blob/develop/src/main/java/eu/h2020/symbiote/model/Resource.java>, populate it with values for our resource. Remember that in this case `resourceURL` that you specify for your resource should point directly to your RAP instance (the same URL you specified in 2.)
 - b. Use some POJO->JSON tools (Jackson, GSON etc.) to change it into JSON and post it to `CloudCoreInterface` endpoint of our platform. Address of the endpoint is

<http://core.symbiote.eu:8101/cloudCoreInterface/v1/platforms/<platformId>/resources> so in case of our platform it is: <http://core.symbiote.eu:8101/cloudCoreInterface/v1/platforms/589dc62a9bddb2d2a7ggab8/resources>

Example of the final JSON representation of our object should look like this:

```
{
  "name": "Sensor1",
  "owner": "PlatformAOwner",
  "description": "This is a test sensor",
  "featureOfInterest": "foil",
  "platformId": "589dc62a9bddb2d2a7ggab8",
  "location":
  {
    "name": "Poznan",
    "description": "Poznan - malta",
    "longitude": 16.940144,
    "latitude": 52.421790,
    "altitude": 100
  },
  "observedProperties":
  [
    "Temperature"
  ],
  "resourceURL": "http://myplatform.eu:8100/"
}
```

- c. Parse the response (which is also *Resource* object) and retrieve id from it. This is the symbloTe generated id of our resource.
 - d. Next step is to inform the RAP about the resource. To do so you need to prepare and send message on exchange *symbloTe.rap* and queue *symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.register_resources*. The message that is expected is again simple JSON which contains two fields: *internalId* and *id*. *InternalId* is your platform's internal id of the resource and *id* is symbloTe-generated id of the resource from previous step.
5. If every step was successful your resource should be accessible the same as resources registered using full stack of symbloTe cloud. You can use tests described in point 9.5.3.

9.6 SymbloTe Core – project build, deployment and usage

symbloTe is a mediator, an intermediary connecting applications and IoT platforms. The basic functionality is that of a registry service which lists platforms, their resources and properties, while also providing a way to map between the platforms' different APIs.

9.6.1 Project Build & Deployment

- Install RabbitMQ server:

- RabbitMQ is a message queue framework (uses AMQP) that lets our services exchange informations and events.
- After installation RabbitMQ server should be active in the background without necessity to start it every time you want to run the project.
- Details: <https://www.rabbitmq.com/download.html> (step by step with APT for Ubuntu/Debian)
- Install MongoDB server:
 - Before you can launch the project, MongoDB server has to be up and running on your machine.
 - It stores the data in the default directory: '/data/db', which (if it does not exist yet) you have to create before launching the server. You can remove all of its contents if you want to rerun clean project.
 - After executing, Mongo server should show status 'waiting for connections on port 27017'.
 - Details: <https://www.mongodb.com/download-center> (step by step with APT for Ubuntu/Debian)
- Clone the Config Properties repository:
 - `git clone` the `CoreConfigProperties` repository to directory: `"{user.home}/git/symbiote/"` (or any other you want, just make sure to change the path in `CoreConfigService bootstrap.properties`)
- Clone the rest of the components:
 - If you just want to deploy but not develop/commit any changes, you can get all components straight from the superproject: `git clone --recursive https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SymbioteCore.git`
 - If you want to download the repos for development purposes, you need to clone them individually into separate folders
 - For the symbloTe Core you need the components: *CoreConfigService*, *Eureka*, *Zipkin*, *Administration*, *Registry*, *Search*, *CoreResourceMonitor*, *CoreResourceAccessMonitor*, *CoreAuthenticationAuthorizationManager*, *CoreInterface*, *CloudCoreInterface*
- Build the components:
 - Remember to change the path in *CoreConfigService bootstrap.properties* if you have changed the *CoreConfigProperties* location
 - Build everything using gradle: `gradle build` (or `gradle build -x test` to skip tests)
 - Resulting jars are in `build/libs` directory

- To execute the compiled jars, do:
`java -jarbuild/libs/<component_name>.jar`
- Run the services in order:
 - Run *CoreConfigService* first
 - Run *EurekaService* second
 - Run *ZipkinService* third
 - Run all remaining components in whichever order you like
 - Check that they were deployed successfully in the *Eureka* panel:
localhost:8761/

9.6.2 Accessing a resource

An application can use a resource by following these steps:

1. Search for resource

To search for resource we need to create a query to the symbloTe Core. In our example we use `http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/query` endpoint and provide parameters for query. All possible query parameters can be seen below:

```
Query parameters {
    platform_id:           String
    platform_name:        String
    owner:                 String
    name:                  String
    id:                    String
    description:           String
    location_name:         String
    location_lat:          Double
    location_long:         Double
    max_distance:          Integer
    observed_property:     List<String>
}
```

NOTES:

- To query using geospatial properties, all 3 properties need to be set: `location_lat` (latitude), `location_long` (longitude) and `max_distance` (distance from specified point in meters).
- Text parameters allow substring searches using "*character which can be placed at the beginning and/or end of the word to search for*". For example querying for `name: Sensor` finds all resources with name starting with `Sensor`, and search for `name: 12` will find all resources containing string "12" in its name. Using substring search can be done for the following fields:
 - `name`
 - `platform_name`

- owner
- description
- location_name
- observed_property

For our example lets search for resources with name *Sensor1*. We can do this by sending an HTTP GET request on symbloTe Core Interface: <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/query?name=Sensor1>. Response contains a list of resources fulfilling the criteria:

```
[
  {
    "platformId": "589c783a9bddd2d2a7gea92",
    "platformName": "PlatformA",
    "owner": "PlatformAOwner",
    "name": "Sensor1",
    "id": "589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8",
    "description": "This is a test sensor",
    "locationName": "Poznan",
    "locationLatitude": 52.42179,
    "locationLongitude": 16.940144,
    "locationAltitude": 100,
    "observedProperties": [
      "Temperature"
    ]
  }
]
```

2. Obtaining resource access URL

To access the resource we need to ask symbloTe Core for the access link. To do this, we need to send an HTTP GET request on <http://core.symbiote.eu:8100/coreInterface/v1/resourceUrls?id=589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8>

If we provided the correct id of the resource, we will get a response containing the URL to access the resource:

```
{
  "589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8":
  "http://myplatform.eu:8101/rap/Sensor('589dc62a9bddd2d2a7gga
b8') "
}
```

3. Accessing the resource and triggering fetching of our example data

For an application to access the URL link retrieved from the previous step, it has to send an HTTP GET request to the *Interworking Interface* of the platform, which forwards the access request to the RAP component. RAP searches for the a resource with the *internal id* specified in the URL. The method created in section 2.1 is then called to retrieve the value of the resource.

HTTP GET on `http://myplatform.eu:8101/rap/Sensor('589dc62a9bddd2d2a7ggab8')` results in:

```
{
  "headers": {
    "X-Application-Context": [
      "ResourceAccessProxy:8100"
    ],
    "Content-Type": [
      "application/json;charset=UTF-8"
    ],
    "Transfer-Encoding": [
      "chunked"
    ],
    "Date": [
      "Wed, 15 Feb 2017 14:12:49 GMT"
    ]
  },
  "body": {
    "resultTime": 1487167969540,
    "resourceId": "symbIoTeID1",
    "samplingTime": 1487167968540,
    "location": {
      "longitude": 16.940144,
      "latitude": 52.42179,
      "altitude": 100,
      "name": "Poznan",
      "description": "Poznan test"
    },
    "obsValue": {
      "value": 7,
      "obsProperty": {
        "label": "Temperature",
        "comment": "Air temperature"
      }
    },
    "uom": {
      "symbol": "C",
      "label": "degree Celsius",

```

```
        "comment": null
      }
    },
    "statusCode": "OK",
    "statusCodeValue": 200
  }
```